

Scientific article

How do wind farm layout design, control and co-design optimization compare in mitigating external and internal wake effects?

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Abstract: *As wind farms are increasingly developed in close proximity, wake interactions between neighboring farms are becoming a critical factor that can reduce the overall plant performance. To address the need for effective mitigation strategies, this study systematically investigates the potential of layout design, wind farm control, and control-layout co-design optimization to mitigate both internal and external wakes. Using the IEA Wind 2200-22-MW reference cluster as a case study, the results indicate that wind farm control has limited effectiveness in mitigating wakes generated by neighboring wind farms. In contrast, layout design and control-layout co-design may provide moderate performance improvements, but only in cases of large neighboring wind farms. The results also highlight that uncertainties in the design assumptions about neighboring wind farms and the eventual applicability of the control strategy can generate losses substantially larger than the anticipated benefits. These findings underline the importance of incorporating such risks into the design process.*

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